

IN-HABIThon

IN-HABIT - Inclusive Health and Wellbeing in Small and Medium-sized Cities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

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IN-HABIT ACTIVITY GUIDE with Design for Change (DFC)

Introduction:

With the aim of strengthening the legacy of the IN-HABIT project, this guide has been conceived as a practical and strategic tool following five years of research, local action, and international collaboration. Throughout the project's development, the main challenges and barriers to promoting health and wellbeing in vulnerable urban contexts —particularly in small and medium-sized cities— have been clearly identified.

The main objective of this guide is to facilitate the replication of participatory spaces that promote the CoCoCo model —co-designed, co-developed, and co-managed— as a way to sustain the impact of IN-HABIT beyond its completion.

In this context, IN-HABIThon organizers take as a starting point the VIS (Visionary and Integrated Solutions) identified within the project. Based on the urban challenges that gave rise to these solutions, each participating organization selects the specific issue they wish to address. The IN-HABIThon is thus launched as a co-creation process to explore new ways of tackling real-life challenges. Timing and implementation formats can be adapted to the needs and availability of each team or community.

This guide is complemented by other key documents:

- A detailed description of the solutions adopted within the framework of the project.
- Instructions for participants.
- A compilation of dynamics to facilitate participatory processes.
- A Communication Guide

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- Logistical recommendations for organising hackathons and similar collaborative processes.

IN-HABIThon

The Design for Change Methodology...

- is an opportunity to gain confidence and empathy, based on 'we can do it'.
- is done through a process of experimentation.
- it is done in a different and enriching way.
- it seeks the participation of all people.

You make the project possible

IN-HABIThon ACTIVITY

The aim of this activity is to generate collaborative spaces for reflection and action in which, based on the lessons learned from the IN-HABIT project, ways of promoting health and well-being in medium-sized cities are analysed and proposed. The approach is based on

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identifying and valuing underutilised local resources as drivers of transformation. This guide covers the key aspects of the process, including the necessary preconditions (especially in terms of communication), the methodological keys to effective facilitation, the suggested sequence of steps for carrying out the activity, and possible follow-up actions.

About INHABIT

INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies (IN-HABIT) is a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme that aims to identify visionary and integrated solutions to promote inclusive health and well-being in small and medium-sized cities. In each of the four pilot cities, the project investigates how the mobilisation of undervalued existing resources (such as culture and heritage, food, the link between people and animals, and art and the environment) can contribute to improving health and well-being, with a focus on gender equality, diversity, inclusion and social justice.

About DESIGN FOR CHANGE

As a facilitator of this activity, your role will be key in accompanying young people in a process in which they can put their own ideas into practice to transform their environment. Design for Change (DFC) is based on a simple and powerful premise: every girl, boy or young person can say "I Can!" when given the space and tools to do so. This approach allows them to feel like protagonists of change, based on their own concerns.

The DFC methodology is designed so that anyone can facilitate it, regardless of the educational level or age of the group. Throughout the process, young people develop fundamental skills such as empathy, creativity, critical thinking, teamwork and shared leadership. It is a learning path that promotes confidence, active listening and collaboration.

The proposal is built on the idea that "We Can," because change is generated in community. As a facilitator, your role will be to create a safe space where respect, observation, and active

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participation are the pillars of the work. In this way, each participant will be able to experience their own process of empowerment and become an agent of change through action.

One of the great values of the DFC approach is that it invites us to live with uncertainty and seek solutions from a flexible perspective, without presupposing answers. During the process, each young person can take on different leadership roles, according to their strengths, in an environment that recognises the diversity of talents and ways of contributing.

This approach places young people at the centre of learning, giving them autonomy and responsibility for what they build. It also promotes commitment to the community, the active participation of all those involved, and total openness to diversity of issues, cultures and perspectives. Every young person has something unique to contribute: their own perspective, their experience, their voice. And at Design for Change, every voice counts.

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1. What are the keys to carrying out the activity?

Trust the process

We often tend to solve problems in a linear fashion, moving directly from the problem to the solution. However, the Design for Change methodology proposes a different way of approaching challenges, integrating both moments of convergence and divergence. This dynamic is especially important in processes that involve creativity: first, the range of options is opened up (divergence) to explore multiple possibilities, and then the most appropriate ones are selected (convergence).

This approach can generate some discomfort, as broadening the spectrum of options increases uncertainty. It is common for the group to feel "lost" or that they are not moving in the right direction. As a facilitator, it is important to remember and convey that this feeling of "fog" is not an obstacle, but a sign that the creative process is working.

To facilitate this process, we suggest **organising the group into teams of 4 to 6** people. This will facilitate collaborative work, the exchange of ideas and more active and equitable participation. Your role will be to accompany these moments of exploration and discovery, maintaining a balance between openness and focus.

Empathy

One of the main objectives of this activity is to develop the ability to put oneself in other people's shoes. As a facilitator, encourage the group to observe and analyse reality from multiple perspectives, as this skill broadens understanding of the environment and strengthens critical thinking. Empathy plays a central role in this process, and its starting point is clear: listening.

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Listening actively and with openness is the first step in connecting with other people's real needs, thus laying the foundation for designing meaningful solutions.

Encourage collaboration

As a facilitator, remember that encouraging collaboration among participants is key to the development of the activity. Working as a team is not only enriching, but also allows for the generation of more comprehensive and sustainable ideas. However, it is important to bear in mind that collaboration requires practice, empathy and generosity. Support the group so that they can reach agreements, make shared decisions and value the common good over individual preferences. Proposing and accepting different ideas with a constructive attitude will strengthen the team and enrich the process.

Listening as a foundation

The Design for Change methodology is based on active listening as a fundamental tool for collective construction. Encourage the group to listen carefully and consider the opinions of others as valid, even when they do not coincide with their own. This attitude will allow each person to feel part of something bigger than themselves: a team, a community, a shared experience. It facilitates spaces where all voices are heard and taken into account, remembering that the most valuable thing is not to impose an individual idea, but to build collective proposals that reflect the diversity of the group.

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2. Work process

2.1. Five-phase development

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Each phase is divided into several steps.

	<p>What do you think is relevant about the challenge? Organise the information Identify areas for action Choose a focus Gain understanding Summarise what you have learned Specify the challenge</p>	<p>This is the phase in which you investigate to understand the environment surrounding the challenge. It is based on empathy and understanding.</p>
	<p>Propose lots of ideas Choose the best solutions Make a prototype Finalise your proposal</p>	<p>This involves generating and developing ideas to improve the situations analysed in the previous phase, and preparing to put them into practice.</p>
	<p>Individual action plan Possible implementation</p>	<p>For this activity, the idea generated is presented so that the proposals for change can be put into practice.</p>
	<p>Reflect on what you have learned</p>	<p>What we have learned can be applied to any other situation that arises.</p>
	<p>Share your idea</p>	<p>Share your solution with the world.</p>

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2.2. Feel

TO FEEL, YOU NEED TO PERCEIVE, INTERPRET AND UNDERSTAND THE WORLD WE LIVE IN

In the first phase of the process, based on the information you have provided, they will identify the aspects to work on.

FEEL is a research stage in which, through observation, listening and analysis, knowledge about the problem and its environment is enriched.

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2.2.0 Connecting with the challenge

In the document detailing the solutions adopted within the framework of the project (VIS), you will find the various challenges identified during the project's implementation, along with contextual information to support their understanding.

Once you have chosen the challenge to work on, share it with the participants. If possible, involve local people who can provide first-hand information about the specific environment, as this will be invaluable in enriching the work. If this is not feasible, you can start the activity with the data and information already available. As a facilitator, your role will be to ensure that the group has a good understanding of the context of the challenge before starting to generate ideas.

2.2.1 What do you think is relevant about the challenge?

Although it would be ideal to have an in-depth understanding of the people you are designing for and their specific context, on this occasion we will work with the information provided in advance. After a brief period of individual reflection, ask them to write down everything they consider relevant and to note each observation on a post-it note, following these guidelines:

- Write complete sentences in clear handwriting.
- Use one sticky note for each piece of information.
- Avoid formulating solutions; focus on data, observations or relevant aspects.
- Whenever possible, use the same type of marker or pen so that the author of each post-it note cannot be identified, thus facilitating an environment of trust.

Then, invite them to read aloud what they have written and place it in no particular order on the large sheet of paper. This is a time to gather "facts", not ideas. It is important to avoid discussing

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or evaluating the contributions: this is not yet the time to look for solutions, but to gather as many different perspectives as possible.

Materials needed: post-it notes, markers, flipchart or equivalent.

2.2.2 Organise the information

At this point in the process, the group will find itself with a large number of seemingly random sticky notes. Guide the group to start sorting them as a team, grouping together observations that they think are related. This is an ideal time to encourage conversation and the exchange of views.

It is important to remember that the aim is not to classify the information, but to identify possible areas for action. Avoid groupings such as 'positive/negative' or 'cause/effect', as this is not the objective of this phase.

Once grouped, each set of observations will become an "information cloud" based on the criteria shared by the group. Don't worry if some post-its don't fit into any group: they can also function as an individual cloud.

2.2.3 Identify areas for action

From each cloud, invite the group to identify an area for improvement. To do this, ask them to write a sentence that summarises what the cloud contains, always using a subject and a predicate. This exercise may require several proposals before the final wording is agreed upon. You can also suggest incorporating drawings or symbols to support the visual expression of the focus.

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Remember: this is not yet about finding solutions, but about clearly formulating what needs to be addressed. If you have a cloud with only one post-it note, **ask the group to read it** and discuss its relevance in order to come up with a consensus sentence.

Materials: Coloured markers

2.2.4 Choose a focus

Once all the focus areas have been defined, it is time to prioritise. We recommend a two-round voting process:

1. Ask the group to cast two or three votes on the focus areas they consider most relevant.
2. From among the most voted, hold a second round of voting with one vote per person.

You can include additional criteria such as feasibility, expected impact or external priorities if necessary.

2.2.5 Gain understanding

This step is key. Often, effort is spent on solving the wrong problem. To avoid this, encourage the group to delve deeper into the chosen focus.

If you have access to experts or people directly involved in the issue, arrange for the group to interview them. If this is not possible, suggest at least a little online research. If there are local participants, facilitate this meeting.

Suggest that the group prepare open-ended questions that promote conversation and active listening. The aim is not to validate preconceived ideas, but to understand how those closest to the situation experience it.

Guiding questions:

- Who is affected by this situation?

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- How do these people experience it?
- What do they feel, think and do in this situation?

Remember to document as much as possible: notes, drawings, photos or videos (always with prior permission).

Materials: notepad, interview script. Below is a simple script and some tips:

Suggested interview script for young participants

BEFORE YOU START:

Remind them that they need to explain who they are, why they want to do this interview, and ensure that they consent to you taking notes, photos or recording. It is important to create an atmosphere of trust and respect.

1. LET'S GET TO KNOW EACH OTHER A LITTLE (Icebreaker questions)

- What do you like to do in your free time?
- What do you value most about your neighbourhood/community?

2. UNDERSTANDING THE SITUATION (Open-ended questions related to the chosen challenge)

- How do you live with or experience this situation in your daily life?
- What worries or bothers you most about this issue?
- Can you tell us about a specific moment or experience related to this?
- Do you think this situation has changed in recent years? Why?

3. LOOKING TO THE FUTURE (Questions to identify desires, ideas or motivations)

- How would you like this situation to be in a few years?
- What do you think would need to change?

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- What should be taken into account to improve this situation?

4. TO FINISH (Questions to gather emotions or personal impressions)

- Is there anything else you would like to share with us?

Tips for the interview:

- Encourage the group to listen without interrupting and to take notes of key ideas or powerful phrases.
- It is useful to designate someone from the group as the interviewer and another person to take notes or record (if permission has been requested).
- Notes should be taken clearly, avoiding personal interpretations.

2.2.6 Summarise what you have learned

Once the research has been carried out, **guide the group** to organise and summarise what they have discovered:

- What exactly is the situation?
- Who is affected and how?
- What have they learned about the emotions, thoughts and behaviours of the people involved?

If the initial interpretation of the problem has changed, **help them to rephrase** the sentence that summarised the focus. This new wording should clearly and visually reflect what they have learned. Use a new sheet of paper and make sure it is clearly visible.

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2.2.7 Specify the challenge

To close this phase, help them translate the focus of action into a challenging question using the formula:

How could we... *[increase, reduce, improve, change, optimise, eliminate, create, achieve]* so that... *[users]* solve the... *[need]* in... *[context]*?

Example: How could we *get older people to take advantage of technology for their celebrations* when their relatives cannot visit them?

Make sure they come up with several challenges and choose the one they find most appealing and motivating.

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2.3. Imagine

LET YOUR IMAGINATION BE THE FIRST STEP TO BUILD A NEW REALITY

This phase is aimed at coming up with proposals that respond to the identified challenge.

IMAGINE is a creative and collaborative stage in which unexpected skills emerge, especially if an environment of trust, freedom and listening is created.

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2.3.1 Propose lots of ideas

Invite the group to generate as many ideas as possible. The more ideas, the more chances of finding good solutions. Encourage bold proposals, even those that seem unfeasible: this is the time to imagine without limits and without judgement.

Remember that all ideas are valid at this stage; it is not about judging, but about building collectively on other people's ideas. You can use techniques such as 'crazy ideas', encouraging approaches that, although they may seem impossible, could lead to more viable or inspiring ideas. You can take an idea that has been said and break it down into two, exaggerate it, transform it, combine it with others... To do this, it is essential to listen to each other: respect each other's turn to speak and try to express yourself simply and clearly.

When brainstorming begins, a few tentative suggestions emerge first (sparking), then many more (raining!) and finally it sparks again. Be patient and trust that ideas will come! One technique that helps with divergence is crazy ideas: when a certain amount of time has passed and ideas start to run out, participants are asked to come up with crazy ideas, which by definition are those that appear impossible to implement; however, they can open up new possibilities that either give rise to ideas that can be implemented or are used in the prototype.

Materials: Flipchart paper or equivalent and coloured markers

2.3.2 Choose the best solutions

Once the ideas have been generated, ask the group to vote individually for the ones they like best. You can organise the vote in two rounds to reach a greater consensus.

Ask them to vote individually for the proposals they like best, find most interesting or appealing. One or two votes per person is sufficient, although this depends on how many ideas have been generated. Then hold a second vote on the most popular ideas, with one vote per person.

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Next, ask them to choose the most voted ideas and comment on them, imagining which ones can best help solve the problem.

Emphasise that the choice should be based on their personal connection to the proposal, what excites them most, and its potential for change.

2.3.3 Make a prototype

The prototype is an initial representation of the idea. It can be a drawing, a simple model or any form that helps to explain and visualise it. Ideally, you should have some simple materials available for prototyping: cardboard, scissors, stickers, wool, etc.

Guide the group to prepare their prototype and share it with another team. The receiving group should offer feedback using this formula: "What we found most interesting is... and also, you could..."

The group receiving the feedback can only respond with "Thank you!" This gesture reinforces an open and receptive attitude towards improvement. We have a natural tendency to justify our work and therefore do not appreciate the feedback we receive. As feedback is a gift, we should be grateful for it.

Next, the other team explains their prototype and is given feedback using the same formula.

2.3.4 Refine your idea

Facilitate a final reflection so that they can summarise their proposal. You can use this structure:

What the idea consists of.

A short sentence that summarises the proposal.

Who will it help?

Which users will benefit from the solution.

What will it be used for?

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What do you want to achieve once it is implemented?

What is needed to implement it.

Needs, both in terms of material resources and collaboration from people outside the team.

The form is titled "IMAGINE Make your proposal concret" and features logos for "IN-HABIT" and "DESIGN for CHANGE ESPAÑA". It contains six text input fields arranged in two columns. The left column fields are: "Challenge", "What is the idea?", "Who are you going to help?", and "What good will it do?". The right column fields are: "What does it take to make it happen?" and "Prototype".

You can find this template in the same location where this guide was downloaded.

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2.4. Do

THE MOST VALUABLE LESSONS LEARNED BEGIN WITH REAL ACTIONS FOR CHANGE

Although actions are usually carried out in the real world at this stage, for this activity your idea may remain 'just' a proposal. Nevertheless, encourage them to individually assess which aspect of their idea they can implement, even if only on a small scale.

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2.4.1 Take action

As a general rule, the prototype designed will not be able to be implemented during the time allocated for this activity (although some of the ideas may be implemented at a later date). However, it is important to encourage them to take action. For this reason, the following activity is proposed.

Individual Action Plan

Ask them to individually create part of the prototype, so that they become true agents of change. To do this, they can fill in the following template:

You can find this template in the same location where this guide was downloaded.

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2.5. Evaluate

REFLECTING ON OUR ACTIONS HELPS US GROW

For this activity, we will focus on learning.

EVOLÚA is a stage that combines evolution and evaluation, in which we look to the future to imagine new actions that can enrich the work we have done.

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2.5.1 Reflect on the activity

We are going to focus on what you have learned from the process. Share your thoughts with the other members of your team and then with the rest of the participants in the activity.

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2.6. Share

SHARE THE EXPERIENCES WE HAVE HAD BUILD OUR STORY

Share your experience on social media, mentioning the IN-HABIT project (@in_habit2020 and @INHABIT_H2020) and Design for Change Spain (@dfcspain).

SHARING is a way to highlight the value of the work done. It is worth the effort to be told and can inspire others. The goal is for the solution to be used by as many people as possible.

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2.6.1 Share your solution

In addition to sharing the solution with the participants in the activity, they can be encouraged to create audiovisual material to publicise the solution they have designed and share it on social media, tagging @in_habit2020, @INHABIT_H2020 and @dfcspain.

2.6.2 We disseminate your solution (optional)

If ideas with real potential for implementation emerge during the IN-HABIThon, you could explore with participants how to follow up on them: seek institutional support, share them with interested entities or present them in other spaces.

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APPENDIX 1

Schedule for completing the process in 4 hours

Phase/Activity	Time
Feel 2.2.0 Connecting with the challenge 2.2.1 What do you think is relevant about the challenge? 2.2.2 Organise the information 2.2.3 Identify areas for action 2.2.4 Choose a focus 2.2.5 Gain understanding 2.2.6 Summarise what you have learned 2.2.7 Specify the challenge	(45 minutes + 70 minutes optional) 5 minutes 15 minutes 5 minutes 10 minutes 5 minutes 60 minutes 10 minutes 5 minutes
Imagine 2.3.1 Propose many ideas 2.3.2 Choose the best solutions 2.3.3 Make a prototype 2.3.4 Finalise your idea	(35 minutes) 10 minutes 5 minutes 10 minutes 10 minutes
Take action 2.4.1 Take action	(5 minutes) 5 minutes
Develop 2.5.1 Reflect on the activity 2.5.2 Develop your solution	(5 minutes + 20 minutes optional) 5 minutes 20
Share 2.6.1 Share your solution 2.6.2 We share your solution (optional)	(20 minutes) after the session 10 minutes 10

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APPENDIX 2

Key points for facilitation

Through our experience, we have identified these keys to facilitating the activity:

- The essence of facilitation lies in **listening** and observing when the group needs it, and without attachment, i.e. not trying to impose one's own opinion.
- The role of the facilitator is to **become a guide**, so that the participant is the protagonist, encouraging everyone to participate without forcing anyone. It is important to note that this does not mean that the facilitator should disappear, but rather that they should be very aware that they are not there to direct. Going one step further, facilitating means taking an active role, listening, to encourage the participation of everyone in the group whenever necessary: opening up perspectives (when interacting in the work of one of the groups), reflecting on what is heard... Seek to get the most out of the group and develop its potential according to its capabilities.
- **Security and confidence** are key to facilitating. Both are developed through training and practice. Take advantage of every opportunity to practise your facilitation skills.
- Furthermore, it is essential **to explain the objective of each step** of the activity and, as far as possible, show how the process can be applied in other areas of life. This will generate greater interest among participants.
- Throughout the process, it is necessary to be **flexible**, as processes generally allow for movement forwards and backwards.
- It is highly recommended **to define and follow the timing of each activity**, while always paying attention to what is happening and remaining flexible, as mentioned above.
- As a facilitator, you need to **observe what kind of energy is needed** at any given moment. Always keep in mind the phrase "Not by chance, by design" so that you can modify the activities on the fly if necessary. In document DFC ACTIVITIES FOR IN-HABIT

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you will find many activities that you can use depending on the moment and your specific needs.

- The last fundamental aspect we have identified focuses **on taking into account the materials and spaces you are going to use**. Remember that planning is essential.
- Finally, throughout the process, if possible, **visually record what is happening**, as this will help you reconnect with the experience later on.

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APPENDIX 3

Next steps

In general, after this type of activity, the energy generated and the relationships between the participants make it possible to continue the experience. If this is the case, the important thing is to facilitate this. The steps that can be taken could be:

- **Create a private group** on a platform (Facebook, LinkedIn, Slack, etc.): a community where you can register participants and invite them to take action.
- **Encourage participation** in the group you have created: to do this, it helps to upload photos of the event to reconnect with the energy and facilitate participation.
- If the proposed solutions are being followed up, **communicate the progress made**.
- **Support any comments** that arise: it is always nice to see that the ideas being put forward are having an impact.
- Organise some kind of **online meeting** where people can get together again.
- **Launch a survey** that makes it easy to participate and maintain momentum.

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